

On the Fluorination of Organic Compounds. Part I.

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Preparations of organic fluoro-compounds by following the usual methods of halogenation are beset with difficulties.

(i) *Direct substitution of hydrogen by fluorine* is not advantageous as the reacting element is not easily obtainable and all organic substances are vigorously acted upon by fluorine, which brings about a complete disruption of the molecule with the liberation of hydrofluoric acid and charring.

(ii) *Addition of hydrofluoric acid to unsaturated bodies* has equally led to negative results as hydrofluoric acid never adds up to unsaturated linkings. This property of hydrofluoric acid is in accordance with the properties of the halogen hydrides, the reactivity of the hydrogen fluoride being much less than that of hydrochloric acid.

(iii) *Substitution of the hydroxyl group by fluorine* has also been attempted. Direct esterification of alcohol by hydrofluoric acid even in a concentrated solution is not advantageous as was shown by Sidney, Young and Meslans (*Compt. rend.*, 1892, 115, 1080).

The technical difficulties in the employment of hydrofluoric acid, the impossibility of using glass apparatus and consequent necessity of using platinum vessels have generally discouraged the investigations with hydrofluoric acid.

To minimise the difficulties metallic fluorides have often been employed. Thus Moissan (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1891, iii, 5, 456) introduced silver fluoride as the fluorinating agent. Meslans (*Compt. rend.*, 1892, 114, 1020) obtained acetyl fluoride by the action of anhydrous zinc fluoride on acetyl chloride. Swarts (*Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1930, 39, 444) introduced SbF_5 (with SbCl_5 or bromine as catalyst) as well as H_2F_2 as fluorinating agents.

In a recent communication on the ethyl and methyl esters of fluocarbonic acid Sarkar and Goswami (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 537) have employed anhydrous thallic fluoride as the fluorinating agent. They have prepared methyl and ethyl esters of fluocarbonic acid by the action of anhydrous thallic fluoride on the methyl and ethyl esters of chlorocarbonic acid.

In continuation of their work we tried to prepare some new organic fluo derivatives and the present communication describes this attempt.

We have prepared monofluoacetone, ω -fluoacetophenone and fluoacetal by the action of anhydrous thalious fluoride on the corresponding bromo derivatives. The boiling point, density and refractive index of the fluo derivatives are given below.

	B. p.	Density.	Ref. Index.
Fluoacetone	72.5°	d_{24}^{20} , 0.967	1.3693 (21°)
Fluoacetophenone	98°/8 mm.	d_{33}^{20} , 1.154	1.5301 (28.9°)
Fluoacetal	60°/125 mm.	d_{340}^{20} , 1.447	1.4363 (34°)

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fluoacetone.—Bromoacetone (27 g.) was refluxed at 85-95° for 45 hours with powdered anhydrous thalious fluoride (48 g.) mixed with 25 c. c. of dry ether. The upper part of the condenser was fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube. When the reaction was over the product was filtered in a suction pump and the filtrate distilled. It was purified by redistillation (b.p. 72.5°), yield 10 g. (66%). It is a pungent smelling light yellow liquid, slightly soluble in water. (Found: C, 47.01; H, 6.63; F, 24.61. $C_3H_5O_2F$ requires C, 47.3; H, 6.5; F, 25.0 per cent).

Fluoacetone semicarbazone.—Fluoacetone (5 g.) was added to a saturated solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and to this excess of a saturated solution of sodium acetate added. The semicarbazone precipitated out on stirring with a glass rod. It was filtered off, washed with a little water, dried and analysed, m. p. 131.5° (decomp.). It is a white crystalline solid slightly soluble in water. (Found: N, 31.05; F, 14.1. $C_4H_8ON_3F$ requires N, 31.4; F, 14.28 per cent).

Fluoacetophenone.—Bromoacetophenone (20 g.) was refluxed for 45 hours with anhydrous thalious fluoride (23 g.) in 40 c. c. absolute alcohol. The product was then filtered and the filtrate after removing the alcohol on a water-bath, was then distilled at 98°/18 mm., yield 11 g. (79 %). It is a brown pungent smelling, lachrymatory liquid. It forms additive compounds with pyridine and quinoline. (Found: C, 69.35; H, 5.42; F, 13.5. C_9H_7OF requires C, 69.56; H, 5.07; F, 13.75 per cent).

Pyridine addition compound.—Pyridine and fluoacetophenone in equimolecular proportion are dissolved in ether and mixed together. The mixture was slightly warmed when a turbidity appeared. After 48 hours the additive compound precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised from alcohol. It formed white needles, soluble in water, m. p. 161°. (Found: N, 6.04. $C_{13}H_{12}ONF$ requires N, 6.4 per cent).

Quinoline addition compound.—Ethereal solutions of equimolecular quantity of quinoline and fluoacetophenone were mixed together and warmed on a water-bath. After 12 hours the additive compound precipitated out and was recrystallised from alcohol as white needles by the addition of ether. It is soluble in water. It becomes brown at 231°. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{17}H_{16}ONF$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

Fluoacetal.—Bromoacetal (60 g) was mixed with powdered anhydrous thalious flouride (70 g.) and the mixture refluxed on an electric heater for 24 hours. The condenser was provided with a calcium chloride guard tube. When the reaction was over the solution was filtered off and the filtrate distilled at 60°/25 mm. was collected, yield 22 g. (55%). It is a light yellow liquid with a pungent smell. (Found: C, 52.51; H, 9.7; F, 13.7. $C_6H_{13}O_2F$ requires C, 52.9; H, 9.5; F, 13.97 per cent).

Method of Analysis

Estimation of C and H.—The analysis was carried out as recommended by Moissan (*Ann. chim. Phys.*, 1890, vi, 19, 277). The combustion was effected in a current of oxygen in a metal tube of copper by means of a mixture of CuO (80%) and litharge (20%), the latter retaining all fluorine as oxyfluoride.

Estimation of fluorine.—Fluorine was estimated by the method of Chablay modified by Vaughan and Nieuwland (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1931, 3, 274) and later on by Govaert (*Compt. rend.*, 1932, 195, 797).

Estimation of N.—This was done by H. Ter Meulen's method, but the nitrogen in the semicarbazones was estimated by Duma's method.